

PROFESSIONAL FORMATION OF THE PERSONALITY OF MILITARY UNIVERSITY CADETS IN THE PROCESS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TRAINING

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Abstract. *The article deals with the urgent tasks of professional and personal development of cadets of the higher military educational institution. The main meanings of such concepts as «profession», «professional activity», «formation», «professional formation», the main areas in which it is objectively possible to implement self-determination of the military university cadets, as well as the stages of the process of future officer professional formation are revealed.*

Keywords: *professional and personal development, profession, foreign language education, military university, future officer, professional activity, identity, identification process, stages of the process of professional formation of future officer.*

Introduction

Any kind of social activity, primarily in terms of its role for society, requires a deep scientific, theoretical and scientific-practical understanding. The activity of a serviceman needs to be closely studied, which is one of the most paramount due to its social value and moral and personal orientation in any society. In the same sense, the festive congratulation of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the occasion of the 32nd anniversary Day of the formation of the Armed Forces and Defenders of the Motherland says: «We can confidently say that in all the successes and achievements on the way to building New Uzbekistan, there is a great contribution from our Armed Forces, thousands of servicemen who are worthily fulfilling their duty. The professional skills of our army and its authority in the world are growing» [1]. For further development, «... great attention will be paid to improving combat training, knowledge and skills, expanding worldview, improving the professional and cultural level of military personnel» [2].

Materials and Methods

In the course of the research, we relied on the works of both national and foreign authors dealing with the problem of personality formation, including the personality of the cadet, his identity and identification process, as well as the stages of his professional formation.

This material required the use of a theoretical research method, namely, theoretical analysis and scientific justification.

The professional and personal development of a serviceman (cadet, officer) begins in a higher military educational institution, the specifics of which are associated with a strict lifestyle, including the learning process.

The concept of reflected subjectivity of A.V. Petrovsky and V.A. Petrovsky, based on the cultural and historical theory of L.S. Vygotsky and the theory of activity of A.N. Leontiev, allows us to consider the organized educational process as an element that provides social mediation. [3; 4]. Developing the ideas of A.N. Leontiev, the authors propose to introduce an element of mediation in the form of another subject in the first case and an object in the second: S – S -O and

S– O - S into the traditional schemes of the-subject-of-the-object (S-O) and the-subject-of-the-subject (S-S) type of interaction. Such mediation is provided, in particular, in the process of foreign language training, through the organization of communication aimed at mastering foreign language content.

V.A. Petrovsky also highlights «a special human need: the need to be a person – the need for personalization». This need is realized in specific actions aimed at first being meaningful to others and then to oneself as for another. In this case, L.S. Vygotsky's idea of the internalization of external social relations into intrapsychic ones is implemented. This provision is especially significant in the context of training future officers in connection with the pronounced social significance (for others) of their professional activities – their «... service to the state is aimed at protecting its citizens in particular, and society as a whole, from internal and external dangers» [5, p. 52].

Currently, the attention of researchers is increasingly attracted to the study of the phenomenon of identity and the identification process [6;]. In the psychological dictionary, the term «identification» is interpreted in several meanings: assimilation; a mechanism of psychological protection; projection; a mechanism of grouping; a mechanism of identification with a social role. Researchers consider identity either as a result of self-determination, or as a synonym for self-determination. In this issue, we join O.V. Belanovskaya's point of view, who, based on the analysis of different points of view, defines identification as a mechanism for mastering social experience: «Personality is a socio–cultural construct reflecting the social essence of a person. An individual, through an identification mechanism, appropriates social experience and turns into a personality. Personality development is a continuous process that includes, at each stage of mental development, qualitatively new things that arise in the personality. Personality neoplasms include an identification mechanism. The identification mechanism is not constant. It is a variable depending on age and stages of mental development» [7, p. 6]. That is, in the process of training at university, there is a real opportunity to ensure professional self-determination of the individual through the actualization of the identification mechanism. The research notes that professional self-determination of an individual is based on the acceptance of social ethical and psychological requirements for oneself as a representative of a certain profession, on the acceptance of professionally significant values, and it is important to ensure such acceptance pedagogically already at the stage of training cadets in a military university [8].

When developing the research problem, we rely on the interpretation of the concept of profession given by E.A. Klimov. He identifies four main meanings of the concept of «profession» in modern usage:

- the area of application of human forces;
- a community of people engaged in a certain kind of work;
- human preparedness, qualifications;
- activity, the very process of implementing certain functions.

In the current difficult situation in the world, the profession of «military» can be considered as one of the most difficult, brave and courageous professions in modern society. A person who has chosen the life path of a serviceman and «honorably fulfills the highest mission – to defend the Motherland» [1] must have high professionalism, which consists in «consistently successful high-level solutions to the tasks that make up the content of a specialist's activity in a particular field of work» [9]. Becoming a military, a professional is a personal project of the cadet himself.

By implementing this project, he gets to know himself more deeply, sets goals for himself to ascend to higher levels of development and monitors the results obtained, noting failures and difficulties [10].

In another work, E.A. Klimov defines a profession as necessary for society, socially valuable and limited due to the division of labor, the area of application of physical and spiritual forces of a person, giving him the opportunity to receive in return for the labor spent the necessary means of his existence and development [11].

Taking into account the definition of the profession, as well as the scientific understanding of the subject of activity, we note the main areas in which it is objectively possible to exercise self-determination of military university cadets:

the sphere of personality, in which the results of self-determination are recorded in the form of various skills, abilities, as well as values and interests;

a socio-psychological sphere where, through communication in the professional community, a person chooses and assimilates group values, patterns for the formation of professional identity;

self-determination in the field of activity itself, which includes the development of certain skills and qualities, and the formation of the activity itself as a professional one.

When modeling foreign language training, it is envisaged to actualize the self-determination of cadets in these areas to ensure professional and personal development.

Since the study examines the development of a directional character, let's focus on the characteristics of the concept of «professional activity».

Activity is defined as a manifestation of the activity of a person, as well as a manifestation of a person's relationship with the outside world (which is also a manifestation of activity). Professional activity is a certain connection with a specific part of this world (a subject specific to this activity) [12].

F.E. Slyambayev considers military activity as a complex social phenomenon, an integral element of social activity in all spheres of society, as a part of public life, which is a material, sensory-objective activity of people aimed at ensuring military security as the preservation of life, conditions for free physical existence and development of large groups of people, peoples, states [13].

In modern conditions, when the problem of professionalization of the personnel of armed forces that is associated with the development of military cooperation with foreign countries is raised, the organization and conduct of joint exercises, the exchange of military information, the holding of international conferences of the military scientific society, as well as partnership in the training of military personnel, the role of foreign language training of military personnel ready to interact with representatives of other cultural communities is increasing.

The formation of an integral structure of a person's professional activity assumes that specific professional motives become motivating and determining the course of activity, being internal reasons that motivate a person to this activity. Such reasons may be the needs, worldview, beliefs, ideals and interests of the individual, social roles and attitudes. This fully applies to the training of a future officer. The state and society care what motives motivate young men to choose a military profession today, since those who choose it in the future will deal with modern weapons systems and sophisticated military equipment, and be responsible for their use. Thus, A.V. Dubinin and A.M. Borovitsky indicate: «In a modern military school, one of the most important issues of

military education can be considered the motivation of cadets to acquire professional knowledge» [14, p. 259].

Foreign language training, being an integral part of the professional and personal development of a serviceman, can cause a cadet to strive to master the language as a way to assert himself (internal or personal motivation) or to fulfill his civic duty to the Motherland by taking part in various activities related to the development of military cooperation at a high level (external motivation). But unfortunately, as practice shows, many cadets show a desire to learn a foreign language only at the initial stage. Then, when they are overwhelmed by a large flow of information that needs to be learned, plus the absence from classes for official reasons (outfits, business trips) leads to a loss of interest.

The meaning of the profession is predetermined in advance, the profession contains a socially developed meaning – the place of this profession in the system of social division of labor. The socially defined meaning is initially only "known" (in the terminology of Leontiev A.N.), it becomes personal only in the process of mastering, appropriation.

V.A. Ponomarenko argues that for a military man, professionalism begins before mastering the profession. "It is born from the formation of a person's need for a voluntary, free choice of his fate — to overcome himself, to take risks in the interests of others. Developed conscience, freedom, discipline and self - discipline, love of life and will — these are the first moral steps of climbing to the heights of moral values - to protect someone else's life. Thus, the personality of a professional matures within itself and only then its reasonable and sensual content acquires socially significant and professional motivation».

Thus, when a person is engaged in a certain practice, in order to understand what kind of activity he is carrying out, an analysis of the real, driving motives of this activity is necessary.

A certain difficulty for the formation of professional motives through foreign language training of cadets is the fact that in the process of this training, the practice of foreign language communication is carried out, which, as a rule, is not fully realized by students themselves in the context of the profession, remaining for them an educational activity. Combining these two contexts for the implementation of professional and personal development is the task of foreign language training.

All this makes it possible to actualize the concept of «formation» in this study. According to E.F. Zeer, formation is understood as a process of progressive personality change under the influence of social influences, professional activity and one's own activity aimed at self-improvement and self-fulfillment [12]. Formation, according to the author, necessarily implies the need for development and self-development, the possibility and reality of its satisfaction, as well as the need for professional self-preservation. The professional formation of a subject is a part of the ontogenesis of a person from the beginning of the formation of professional intentions to the end of active professional activity. It should be noted that a responsible, pedagogically conditioned and controlled stage of a person's professional development is a period of preparation at university when a person is involved in a variety of professionally significant activities (cognitive, educational–professional, professional, social) to form professionally important knowledge, skills, qualities, behaviors and ways of performing activities. The educational process at a military university is professionally directed, subordinated to the development of methods and experience of professional solution of those tasks that cadets can meet in the practice of officer service. Therefore, in general, the activity of a cadet is an educational and professional activity [15, p. 117].

Accordingly, professional development is the formation of a personality adequate to the requirements of professional activity, in other words, the formation of a professional personality.

V.N. Romashin identified the main stages of the process of professional formation of a future officer in a military university, which are the stages of formation and development of professionally important qualities of an officer among cadets [16, p. 14]:

1. The stage of formation of initial military professional qualities, during which professional adaptation to military service and a new lifestyle takes place. At this stage, cadets, based on basic knowledge of exact sciences (physics, mathematics), develop such professionally significant qualities as the ability to work with graphs, tables, and make calculations, including using a PC. In addition, love for the chosen profession is fostered.

2. The stage of formation and development of general professional qualities. In the course of training, cadets must master the theoretical material of the disciplines of mathematical, natural science and general professional blocks. Cadets develop qualities such as analytical thinking, perseverance, ingenuity, spatial thinking.

3) The stage of formation and development of special professional qualities that allow cadets to independently solve problems in the field of their chosen military specialty.

O.B. Bobkov conditionally divided the process of professional development of cadets of a military university into such stages as general development, approximate professional, general professional, specialized. By the end of each stage, the cadet must rise to a new level of theoretical and practical training, the formation of professional skills, qualities [15, p. 117].

The formation and development of cadets of higher military educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan takes place in two stages:

1. The stage of formation and development of general professional qualities.

At this stage, the cadet's study natural sciences such as mathematics, physics, and humanities: psychology, history and foreign languages.

2. The stage of formation and development of special professional qualities. Exploring the problems of the formation and development of self-awareness.

Results and Discussion

The results of the analysis of scientific works of domestic and foreign experts in pedagogy devoted to the problem of professional and personal development have shown that the process of professional formation is a dynamic and continuous development process in which professionally significant activities such as cognitive, educational and professional are used to form professionally significant qualities and individual ways of performing professional activities.

Conclusion

Thus, having studied the above material, we can conclude that professional and personal development in the process of training cadets can be discussed when the student acts consciously and responsibly, uses his intellectual and creative potential in solving tasks, is able to determine the purpose of the activity in terms of achieving a new level of personal, social and/or professional development, that is, self-determination in three areas mentioned above.

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